

Is Perturbation Theory Enough For Relativistic Corrections?

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In some recent articles in the literature (1),(2) the Schrodinger equation:

$$p^2/2m W(x) + V(x) W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((1))$$

is replaced with an equation using a relativistic momentum operator:

$$[\sqrt{p^2 + m^2} - m] W(x) + V(x)W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((2))$$

The first operator on the LHS of ((2)) is then expanded in powers of $1/(m^2)$. Next, p is replaced with $\hbar/i d/dx$ (or gradient in 3D) and perturbation theory used.

In this note, we consider p^2 as being a conditional average given by:

$$p^2 = [\text{Integral } dp \ f(p) \exp(ipx) \ p^2] / [\text{Integral } dp \ f(p) \exp(ipx)] \quad ((3))$$

The denominator is the wavefunction $W(x)$.

This result should hold for the nonrelativistic case. In the relativistic case, p is replaced everywhere with p_{rel} where $p_{rel} = p / \sqrt{1 - p^2/(m^2)}$

$$p^2_{rel} = \text{Integral } dp_{rel} \ p^2_{rel} (1 + p^2_{rel}/(m^2)) f(p_{rel}) \exp(ip_{rel} x) \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{And } W(x) = \text{Integral } dp_{rel} \ f(p_{rel}) \exp(ip_{rel} x) \quad ((5))$$

To first order, we argue that $\text{Integral } dp_{rel} \ f(p_{rel}) \exp(ip_{rel} x) = \text{Integral } dp \ f(p) \exp(ip x)$, but $\text{Integral } p^2_{rel} f(p_{rel}) dp_{rel} \exp(ip_{rel} x)$ contributes a term. For higher orders, even $\text{Integral } dp_{rel} \ f(p_{rel}) \exp(ip_{rel} x)$ contributes. Thus, we try to argue that one does not only have a change in the p^2_{rel} operator, but one must consider changes of p_{rel} within $\text{Integral } dp_{rel} \ f(p_{rel}) \exp(ip_{rel} x)$ itself. Thus, perturbation theory may not be enough in such cases.

Case of (2)

Consider, as an example, the case of (2) where the Salpeter equation is used with two orders of relativistic corrections. The authors write the two corrections to $p^2/2m$ as:

$$H_1 = -p^4 / (8m^3) \quad \text{and} \quad H_2 = -p^6 / (16 m^5) \quad ((6))$$

These are considered as perturbative corrections to the Schrodinger equation:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_n(x) + V(x) W_n(x) = E_n W_n(x) \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is solved for both E_n and $W_n(x)$ and these are both used in perturbation theory equations.

Replacing $prel$ with $p/\sqrt{1-p^2/(m^2)}$ In the Wavefunction and First Order Correction

Consider the replacement of $prel$ with $p/\sqrt{1-p^2/(m^2)}$ expanded as:

$$prel = p + \frac{1}{2} \frac{p^3}{(m^2)} \quad ((8))$$

$W(x) = \int dp_{prel} f(p_{prel}) \exp(i prel x)$. It seems one may consider a more general case namely

$prel = p + g(p)$ where $g(p)$ is any function of p . This is of the form of a transformation.

As a first argument, assume that $\int P(p_{prel}) dp_{prel} = 1 = \int P(p) dp$ ((10)).

In one dimension, $dp_{prel} = dp(1 + \frac{d}{dp} g)$ and $P(p_{prel}) = P(p) + g(p) \frac{d}{dp} P(p)$.

If ((10)) holds, then:

$$\int dp \{P(p) \frac{d}{dp} g + g(p) \frac{d}{dp} P\} = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{d}{dp} (Pg) = 0$$

$$\text{So} \quad \int dp \frac{d}{dp} [P(p) g(p)] = 0. \quad ((11))$$

This condition is important for the change in the wavefunction as the correction to:

$\int dp_{prel} f(p_{prel}) \exp(i prel x)$ is:

$$\left(\frac{d}{dp} g\right) f(p) \exp(ipx) + g(p) \frac{d}{dp} f(p) \exp(ipx) + f(p) g(p) \frac{d}{dp} \exp(ipx) \quad ((12))$$

$$\text{or:} \quad \frac{d}{dp} [g(p) f(p) \exp(ipx)] \quad ((13)),$$

but this integral is 0. This result holds because d/dp is a linear operator. If one calculates higher orders, this is not expected to be the case, and corrections will enter from $prel$ being written as a function of p in the wavefunction.

$$W(\text{calculated using } prel) = W(\text{calculated using } p) \text{ to first order.} \quad ((14))$$

Another argument is to consider the following. The first order correction is taken from:

$$\left(1 + \frac{3}{2} \frac{p^2}{m^2}\right) \frac{d}{dp} \exp(ipx) \left[1 + ix \cdot \frac{1}{2} \frac{p^3}{(m^2)}\right] \left[f(p) + \frac{p^3}{(2m^2)} \frac{d}{dp} f\right]$$

or

$$\frac{3}{2} p^3 \exp(ipx) f(p) + \exp(ipx) i x \cdot \frac{5p^3}{(m^*m)} f(p) + \frac{p^3}{(2m^*m)} \frac{d}{dp} f \exp(ipx) \quad ((14a))$$

Using

$$\int \frac{d}{dp} \left[\frac{5p^3}{(m^*m)} f(p) \exp(ipx) \right] = 0 \text{ because } f(p) \text{ should die down at } \pm \infty$$

Then ((14a)) integrated becomes 0.

This still leaves the calculation of the first correction from the energy :

$$\frac{1}{2m} \int dp \, p^3 f(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((15))$$

The first order correction seems to be:

$$\frac{1}{2m} \int dp \, p^3 \frac{d}{dp} [g(p) f(p) \exp(ipx)] + \frac{1}{2m} \int dp \, g(p) f(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((16))$$

Here $g(p)$ is $\frac{5p^3}{m^2}$. The first term of ((16)) may be rewritten as:

$$\frac{1}{2} m \int dp \, \frac{d}{dp} [p^3 g(p) f(p) \exp(ipx)] = 0 = \frac{1}{2m} \int dp \, p^3 \frac{d}{dp} [g(p) f(p) \exp(ipx)] + \frac{1}{2m} \int dp \, p^3 g(p) f(p) \exp(ipx) \text{ so:}$$

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \int dp \, p^3 g(p) f(p) \exp(ipx) + \frac{1}{2m} \int dp \, g(p) f(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((17))$$

is the first order correction. Thus, writing p in terms of p seems to have an effect on more than just operators. It seems ((17)) is a first order correction not included in the perturbation method of (1) and (2).

Higher Orders

For the first order, it seems that $\int dp \, p^3 f(p) \exp(ipx)$ gives a contribution, while $\int dp \, f(p) \exp(ipx)$ does not. For higher orders $1/(m^5)$, such as those considered in (2), $\int dp \, f(p) \exp(ipx)$ may also contribute to higher order corrections. For instance, $p = p + \frac{5p^3}{m^*m}$ so $(\Delta p)^2$ is of order $1/(m^4)$. Thus, one should consider second order corrections to $\exp(ipx)$ and $f(p)$.

$\exp(ipx)$ gives a second order correction to $W(x)$ of: $\int dp \, -\frac{1}{8} x^2 p^6 / (m^4) f(p) \exp(ipx) =$

$$\frac{1}{8} (x^2) (1/m^4) (d/dx)^6 W(x)$$

And $f(p)$ gives $\int dp \frac{p^6}{(m^4)} [d/dp d/dp] f(p) \exp(ipx)$

Integrating by parts and assuming $f(p)$ and $d/dp f(p)$ vanish at $\pm p$ infinity yields:

$$\{30 (d/dx)^4 W(x) - 6x (d/dx)^5 W(x) + x^2 (d/dx)^6 W(x) - 6x (d/dx)^5 W(x)\} (1/m^4)$$

When combining with the first order term from kinetic energy operator, i.e. $p^2/2m$, this yields a $(1/m^5)$ correction which is of the same order as the second relativistic operator correction used in (2).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that in going from a relativistic momentum squared, more than the operator changes. In the literature, (2) uses:

$$\sqrt{p^2 + m^2} - m = p^2/2m - p^4/(8m^3) + 1/16 p^6/m^5$$

and considers $p = \hbar/i d/dx$ (or gradient in 3D). The authors treat terms of higher order than p^2 using perturbation theory. In this note, we argue that p^n may be treated using:

$$\int dp p^n f(p) \exp(ipx) \quad \text{and} \quad \int dp p^n f(p) \exp(ipx)$$

The first integral gives a first order correction as well as higher order corrections by converting p to a function of p . The second does not yield a first order correction, but seems to yield a second order one. Thus, expanding p in the Fourier series seems to be as important as expanding the relativistic p operator into a sum of nonrelativistic p (to powers) operators. Thus, perturbation corrections may not account for all changes when adding relativistic corrections to the Schrodinger equation.

References

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